

Dietary Pattern and Nutritional Status of Adolescents in Public Secondary Schools

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Abstract

This study examined the dietary pattern and nutritional status of adolescents in public secondary schools in Ondo East Local Government Area, Ondo State. The study adopted a descriptive survey. Four research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The sample size for the study was one hundred and twelve (112) respondents. The instrument for the collection of data for this research was a structured questionnaire on a 4-point scale. The findings of the study showed that though the average nutritional status of the secondary school students in the study area is normal (54.46%), good proportion of them are malnourished. It can be concluded that based on the findings of this study that there are some factors influencing dietary pattern and nutritional status of adolescents in public secondary schools and that though the average nutritional status of the secondary school students in the study area is normal, their dietary pattern is still however worrisome. It is therefore, recommended that parents should pay close attention to the dietary patterns of their children also, government and non-governmental organizations should collaborate to provide a school feeding for adolescents in secondary schools just as it is practiced with children in primary schools.

Keywords: Adolescents, Dietary pattern, Malnutrition, Nutritional Status, Secondary Schools

Introduction

Adolescents are defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as persons aged 10-19 years World Health Organization. Adolescents are nutritionally vulnerable age groups because of their increased nutritional needs, eating patterns, lifestyles and susceptibility to environmental influences. Therefore, healthy dietary pattern play a fundamental role in growth and development during adolescence (Bull, 2021). However, poor eating habits are often observed in adolescents, whose diets are characterized by a low intake of dairy products, fruit, green vegetables, protein and iron, and a high intake of sugar, soft drinks, and sodium- and energy-dense food items, both in developed and developing countries (Kazapi, 2021).

Inappropriate eating pattern such as consumption of fast food, sugar-sweetened drinks, and excess fat consumption are linked to several undesirable health outcomes. These include type-2 diabetes, hypertension, hypercholesterolemia and other metabolic disturbances, as well as overweight and obesity.

Adolescents constitute a significant proportion of the world's population especially in developing countries accounting for 22.1% of Nigeria's population (UNICEF, 2015). The demographic weight of adolescents and their propensity for risky health behaviours fuels concerns about issues regarding their health coupled with the fact that promoting the health of adolescents today guarantees the health of tomorrow's adult population. Youth Risk Behaviour Surveillance System (2013) reported that the leading causes of morbidity and mortality among adolescents have been linked to the behavioural risks among others that include unhealthy dietary habits.

Adolescents in low-and middle-income countries, such as Nigeria, are at increased risk of under-nutrition (because of inadequate food intake, irregular meals consumption especially skipping breakfast) and over-nutrition because of over-consumption of foods that are high in calorie and fats but poor in nutrients (Gacek, 2013). Certain nutritional problems, such as deficiencies in certain micronutrients, like zinc, calcium, iron and vitamin A, are frequently observed in adolescents in developed and developing countries, including Nigeria (Resnicow, 2021). A certain pattern of eating has been observed to be important for healthy living. People who skip breakfast are likely to have difficulty concentrating by mid-morning and to experience a decrease in intellectual performance (Nicklas, 2014). Also, it is likely that they will consume snacks that are high in fat, salt and sugar at other times of the day to increase their total daily energy intake, this predisposes them to obesity. By contrast, it has been observed that individuals who develop healthy eating habits early on in life are likely to maintain them into adulthood, and to have a reduced risk of developing chronic diseases (World Health Organization; (W.H.O; 2020).

Nutritional status has been defined as an individual's health condition as it is influenced by the intake and utilization of nutrients. In theory, optimal nutritional status should be attained by consuming sufficient, but not in excess sources of energy, essential nutrients, and other food components (such as dietary fiber) not containing toxins or contaminants. Traditionally, efforts to detect poor nutritional status have centered on nutritional deficiencies in populations, since defining or assessing optimal health is difficult. Nutritional deficiency follows a pattern starting with low intake or utilization of one or more nutrients, then progressing to biochemical abnormalities, abnormal growth, abnormal body mass, and, eventually, to full-blown deficiency. Poor nutritional status is not confined to under nutrition. It may also result from excessive intake or inadequate expenditure of food energy, or from excessive intakes of specific nutrients, resulting in acute toxicity or chronic diseases.

During adolescence, there are high nutritional deficiencies and poor eating habit which exposes them to many risk factors leading to the development of chronic diseases such as diabetes, osteoporosis, hypertension, heart diseases, chronic kidney failure, cancer, ulcer, overweight and obesity. It can also bring about reduced capacity for learning and work (Olumakaiye, 2018). Adolescents constitute a significant population (almost one fifth of Nigerian population) that represent a huge potential workforce whose health affect the nation socially and economically. Thus, it is necessary to promote and encourage a healthy eating pattern in adolescents. Providing information on nutrition and the eating habits of adolescents is important in order to identify risky and unhealthy behaviour in this age group. This should help when executing effective intervention programmes to bring about positive changes in food intake and to reduce the occurrence and development of chronic Non Communicable Diseases later in life. Hence, this study was conducted to examine the dietary pattern of adolescent in Ondo East Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study wato examine the dietary pattern and nutritional status of adolescents in public secondary schools in Ondo East Local Government Area, Ondo State. Specifically, the study:

- i. assessed the nutritional status of the adolescents in public Secondary Schools in Ondo East Local Government Area of Ondo State.
- ii. documented the dietary pattern of the adolescents in public Secondary Schools in Ondo East Local Government Area of Ondo State.
- iii. identified the effects of inappropriate dietary pattern among public Secondary Schools in Ondo East Local Government Area of Ondo State.
- iv. examined the possible factors affecting the dietary pattern of adolescents in public Secondary Schools in Ondo East Local Government Area of Ondo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. What is the nutritional status of the adolescents in public Secondary Schools in Ondo East Local Government Area of Ondo State?
- ii. What is the dietary pattern of the adolescents in public Secondary Schools in Ondo East Local Government Area of Ondo State?
- iii. What are the effects of inappropriate dietary pattern among public Secondary Schools in Ondo East Local Government Area of Ondo State?

- iv. What are the possible factors affecting the dietary pattern of adolescents in public Secondary Schools in Ondo East Local Government Area of Ondo State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were generated for testing in the course of the study.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the dietary pattern of the adolescents in public Secondary Schools in Ondo East Local Government Area of Ondo State?

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between the dietary pattern and nutritional status of secondary school students in Ondo East Local Government Area.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the effects of inappropriate dietary pattern between male and female students of public Secondary Schools of in Ondo East Local Government Area of Ondo State.

H₀₄: There is no significant difference in the factors affecting the dietary pattern between male and female students of public Secondary Schools of in Ondo East Local Government Area of Ondo State.

ii. Methodology

The study was carried out in Ondo East Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria. Ondo East is a Local Government Area in Ondo State, Nigeria. Its headquarters are in the town of Bolorunduro. The Local Government occupies an area of approximately 896sq kilometers with a population of 76,096 according to the 2006 population census. This study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of this study was two thousand, seven hundred and fifty one (2751) respondents/students from all public secondary schools in Ondo East Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria Ondo State Teaching Service Commission (2023). The sample size for the study was 4% of the total population. This implied one hundred and twelve (112) respondents. The respondents were purposively selected from each of the schools using random sampling techniques. The major instrument for the collection of data for this research was a 30-item structured questionnaire titled “Dietary Pattern and Nutritional Status of Adolescents Questionnaire (DPNSAQ)” The instruments were designed by the researcher in order to obtain reliable and valid information for the research. The questionnaire consisted of five sections. Section (A) contains information on the demographic data of the respondents while and section B,C,D and E contained items on the research objectives raised for this study. The item were rated on a modified 4-point Likerts scale ranging from Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2, Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1.

Instrument for data collection were designed personally by the researcher and presented to the supervisor for correction and approval. It was validated by three experts from the Department of Home Economics. This was to ensure that the items of the questionnaires measured what they were supposed to measure; necessary corrections were made. After the correction and approval, the researcher went ahead to administer the questionnaire to respondents in the selected schools. Reliability of the instrument was determined by test-retest method. By this method, a trail test was done using thirty (30) respondents who were not part of the sample size. The exercise was repeated after two weeks on the same respondent. The two set of scores was computed statistically using Pearson's product moment correlation coefficient. The instrument were found to have a reliability coefficient of 0.5 (level of confidence interval) which was considered high enough and adequate for the study. The researcher personally administered the questionnaire to the respondents. The researcher stressed that all questions should be answered as honestly as possible, since all their answers given would be treated confidentially. The researcher stayed with the respondents and collected the completed copies immediately to avoid loss of materials. The data collected were analyzed using frequency count, percentage, mean, standard deviation, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC) and independent samples t-test statistics. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research question one to four. Frequency count and percentage were additionally used to answer research question one. The decision rule was based on statistical real limits as shown in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1: Statistical Real Limits for Making Decision of Research Question 1

Real Limits	Decision
≤ 18.49	Underweight
18.50-24.99	Normal
25.00 – 29.99	Overweight
≥ 30.00	Obese

Table 2: Statistical Real Limits for Making Decision of Research Question 2-4

Point on Scale	1	2	3	4
Real Limits	1.00 – 1.49	1.50 – 2.49	2.50 – 3.49	3.50 – 4.00
Recommended Items	Very Inadequate	Inadequate	Adequate	Very Adequate
Less Recommended Items	Almost Adequate	Adequate	Excess	Too Excess
Number of meals in a day	Once	Twice	Thrice	Four times
Usual Source of food	Home	Purchase	Both	NA
Do you skip meals	No	Yes	NA	NA
Which meal do you skip	Breakfast	Lunch	Dinner	NA
Eat in- between meals?	No	Yes	NA	NA
What do you eat?	Snacks	Sweet	Fruits	NA
Do you eat Snack?	No	Yes	NA	NA
Effects and Factors	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree

Key: NA = Not applicable

Hypotheses one was analyzed using PPMC. The r-value was used to decide the extent of relationship, such that any r-value between 0.00 – 0.30 was regarded as low correlation, between 0.31 – 0.60 was regarded as moderate correlation, and between 0.61 – 1.00 was regarded as high correlation. The probability value (p) was used to take decide the significance of the relationship. If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05, the null hypotheses was rejected but if p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypotheses was retained. Hypotheses two and three were tested using Independent samples t-test. The probability value (p) was used to take decide the significance of the difference. If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05, the null hypotheses was rejected but if p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypotheses was retained.

iii. Results

Research Question One: What is the nutritional status of the adolescents in public secondary schools in Ondo East Local Government Area, Ondo State?

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of the Nutritional Status of Adolescents in Public Secondary Schools in Ondo East Local Government Area, Ondo State

Nutritional Status	Range	Frequency	Percentage	\bar{x}	SD
Under Weight	11.72 – 18.37	12	10.71	16.71	1.8065
Normal Weight	19.02 – 24.87	61	54.46	22.03	1.8983
Over Weight	25.51 – 29.59	19	16.96	27.68	1.1813
Obese	30.00 – 60.00	20	17.86	35.76	7.4288
Total	11.72 – 60.00	112	100.00	24.87	6.8025

Keys: \bar{x} = mean, SD = Standard deviation

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Table 3 shows that out of the 112 students, 12 (10.71%) were underweight, 61 (54.46%) had normal weight, 19 (16.96%) were overweight, while 20 (17.86%) were obese. The average nutritional status of the students is normal (\bar{x} = 24.87). The average standard deviation value of 6.8025 indicates that the responses moderately vary from the mean.

Research Question Two: What are the dietary patterns of the adolescents in public secondary schools in Ondo East Local Government Area, Ondo State?

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Food Consumption Frequency of Adolescents in Public Secondary Schools in Ondo East Local Government Area, Ondo State

SN	Food Items	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
Recommended Items				
1	Cereals and cereal product e.g. Rice, Wheat	2.31	1.0990	Inadequate
2	Roots and tubers e.g. Yam, Cocoyam	2.66	1.0951	Adequate
3	Vegetable e.g. Carrots, Cucumber	2.29	1.0858	Inadequate
4	Fruits e.g. Apple, Orange etc.	2.28	1.1327	Inadequate
5	Meat Chicken Pork, beef, veal and turkey	2.51	1.2375	Adequate
6	Eggs and egg products e.g. Chicken egg and Duck egg etc.	2.50	1.1069	Adequate
7	Fish/sea food e.g. Salmon, Tuna and Cod	2.27	1.0653	Inadequate
8	Legumes, nuts and seeds e.g. beans, chickpeas, soybeans, and peanuts.	2.01	0.9153	Inadequate
9	Milk and Milk products e.g. cows goats and sheep	2.15	1.0416	Inadequate
Average		2.27	1.0866	Inadequate
Less-Recommended Items				
10	Oils and fats e.g. vegetable oil and animal fats etc.	2.42	1.1282	Adequate
11	Condiments e.g. ketchup, mustard and chocolate sauce etc.	2.63	1.2155	Excess
12	Soft drinks e.g. water, colas, lemon-lime and energy drinks etc.	2.38	1.1321	Adequate
Average		2.48	1.1586	Adequate

Keys: \bar{x} = mean, SD = Standard deviation

Source: Field Survey (2023) Type equation here.

Table 4 reveals that out of the recommended food items, the students inadequately consume cereals and cereal product, roots and tubers, vegetable, fruits, fish and sea foods, legumes, nuts and seeds, and milk and milk products (\bar{x} = 2.01 – 2.31). They, however, consume meat and eggs adequately (\bar{x} = 2.50 – 2.51). On the other hand, out of the less recommended food items, they consume oils and fats and soft drinks adequately (\bar{x} = 2.38 – 2.42), but they consume condiments excessively (\bar{x} = 2.63). Summarily, they consume recommended food items inadequately (\bar{x} = 2.27), while they consume less recommended food items adequately (\bar{x} = 2.48). The average standard deviation values of 1.0866 and

1.1586 for recommended and non-recommended food items respectively indicate that the responses moderately vary from the mean.

Table 5: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Meal Patterns of Adolescents in Public Secondary Schools in Ondo East Local Government Area, Ondo State

SN	Food Items	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1	Number of meals in a day	2.80	0.9665	Thrice
2	Usual Source of food	1.74	0.8878	Purchase
3	Do you skip meals	1.50	0.5023	Yes
4	Which meal do you skip	1.78	0.7794	Lunch
5	Do you eat in- between meals	1.59	0.4949	Yes
6	What do you eat?	1.77	0.8902	Sweets
7	Do you eat Snack?	1.76	0.4310	Yes

Keys: \bar{x} = mean, SD = Standard deviation

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Table 5 shows that averagely the students eat three meals in a day, sometimes skip lunch, got their food majorly through purchase, eat sweets in-between means and consume snacks. The standard deviation values ranging from 0.4310 to 0.9665 indicate that the responses moderately vary from the mean.

Research Question Three: What are the effects of inappropriate dietary pattern among public Secondary Schools in Ondo East Local Government Area, Ondo State?

Table 6: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Effects of Inappropriate Dietary Pattern among Public Secondary Schools in Ondo East Local Government Area, Ondo State

SN	Items	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1.	Inadequate dietary patterns can negatively impact the overall health of adolescents causing diseases	3.05	1.0974	Agree
2.	Poor nutritional status can lead to decreased academic performance among adolescents.	3.17	1.1141	Agree
3.	Inadequate access to healthy food options in public schools can contribute to unhealthy eating habits among adolescents	3.01	1.1586	Agree
4.	Nutritional education in public schools can hinder adolescents' ability to make informed dietary choices.	2.82	1.1407	Agree
5.	Inappropriate Dietary Patterns can result in unhealthy adulthood	3.00	1.1779	Agree
	Average	3.01	1.1377	Agree

Keys: \bar{x} = mean, SD = Standard deviation

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Table 6 reveals that the students agreed to the five statement items (Average \bar{x} = 3.01) on the effects of inappropriate dietary pattern. In other words, they agreed that inadequate dietary patterns can negatively impact the overall health of adolescents by causing diseases (\bar{x} = 3.05), lead to decreased academic performance (\bar{x} = 3.17), contribute to unhealthy eating habits among adolescents (\bar{x} = 3.01), hinder their ability to make informed dietary choices (\bar{x} = 2.82), and result in unhealthy adulthood (\bar{x} = 3.00). The average standard deviation value of 1.1377 indicates that the responses moderately vary from the mean.

Research Question Four: What are the possible factors affecting the dietary pattern of adolescents in public Secondary Schools in Ondo East Local Government Area, Ondo State?

Table 7: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Factors affecting the Dietary Pattern among Public Secondary Schools in Ondo East Local Government Area, Ondo State

SN	Items	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1.	Economic status can significantly affect the dietary choice of adolescents	3.14	1.1768	Agree
2.	Financial constraints of the parents often prevent availability of adequate nutrition to adolescents	3.13	1.0408	Agree
3.	The cultural background of adolescents significantly influences their food choices as a result of taboos placed on certain foods	2.95	1.1612	Agree
4.	Exorbitant cost of nutritious food impacts the dietary choices of adolescents	2.75	1.2412	Agree
5.	Adolescents preference for sweetened meals such as junks, carbonated drinks among others	2.94	1.1569	Agree
6.	Adolescents food choices are based on parental preference	2.83	1.1616	Agree
	Average	2.96	1.1564	Agree

Keys: \bar{x} = mean, SD = Standard deviation

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Table 7 reveals that the students agreed to the six statement items (Average \bar{x} = 2.96) on the factors affecting their dietary pattern. In other words, they agreed that their dietary patterns are affected by economic status (\bar{x} = 3.14), financial constraints of the parents (\bar{x} = 3.13), cultural background (\bar{x} = 2.95), exorbitant cost of nutritious food (\bar{x} = 2.75), personal preference for sweetened meals (\bar{x} = 2.94), and parental preference (\bar{x} = 2.83). The average standard deviation value of 1.1564 indicates that the responses moderately vary from the mean.

Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between the dietary pattern and nutritional status of secondary school students in Ondo East Local Government Area.

Table 8: PPMC of Dietary Pattern and Nutritional Status of Secondary School Students in Ondo East Local Government Area

Variables	\bar{x}	SD	r	df	ρ	α	Decision
Dietary Pattern	2.32	0.4479					Positive but low
Nutritional Status	24.87	6.8025	0.04	110	0.67	0.05	and insignificant relationship

Keys: \bar{x} = mean, SD = Standard deviation, r = correlation coefficient, df = degree of freedom, ρ = probability value of significance, α = alpha value of significance

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Table 8 shows a correlation coefficient of 0.04 which implies a positive but low relationship. A p-value of 0.67 was obtained at 0.05 of significance, which shows that the relationship is not significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis that “there is no significant relationship between the dietary pattern and nutritional status of secondary school students in Ondo East Local Government Area” was retained.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the effects of inappropriate dietary pattern between male and female students of public Secondary Schools of in Ondo East Local Government Area of Ondo State.

Table 9: Independent Samples T-Test of Difference in the Effects of Inappropriate Dietary Pattern between Male and Female Students

Variables	N	\bar{x}	SD	t	df	ρ	α	Decision
Male	58	2.91	0.8495					Not Significant
Female	54	3.12	0.7948	-1.337	110	0.18	0.05	

Keys: \bar{x} = mean, SD = Standard deviation, t = calculated t-value, df = degree of freedom, ρ = probability value of significance, α = alpha value of significance

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Table 9 shows the mean effects of inappropriate dietary pattern were higher for female (\bar{x} = 3.12) than male (\bar{x} = 2.91). A p-value of 0.18 was obtained at 0.05 of significance, which shows that the difference is not significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis that “there is no significant difference in the effects of inappropriate dietary pattern between male and female students of public Secondary Schools of in Ondo East Local Government Area of Ondo State” was retained.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference in the factors affecting dietary pattern between male and female students of public Secondary Schools of in Ondo East Local Government Area of Ondo State.

Table 10: Independent Samples T-Test of Difference in the Factors Affecting Dietary Pattern between Male and Female Students

Variables	N	\bar{x}	SD	t	df	ρ	α	Decision
Male	58	2.86	0.84627	-1.282	110	0.20	0.05	Not Significant
Female	54	3.06	0.79645					

Keys: \bar{x} = mean, SD = Standard deviation, t = calculated t-value, df = degree of freedom, ρ = probability value of significance, α = alpha value of significance

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Table 10 shows the mean factors affecting dietary pattern was higher for female (\bar{x} = 3.06) than male (\bar{x} = 2.86). A p-value of 0.20 was obtained at 0.05 of significance, which shows that the difference is not significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis that “there is no significant difference in factors affecting dietary pattern between male and female students of public Secondary Schools of in Ondo East Local Government Area of Ondo State” was retained.

iv. Discussion of Findings

Findings to research question one show that the average nutritional status of the secondary school students in Ondo East Local Government Area is normal, though a good proportion of them are malnourished. Specifically, (12(10.72%) were underweight, (61(54.46%) had normal weight, (19(16.96%) were overweight, while (20(17.86%) were obese. The values obtain for these study were higher than the report of the study carried out in Lagos as reported by Olatona et al., (2020) whom reported underweight (5.4%), overweight (10.7%) and obese (5.3%) while the reported value obtained in this study was lower than the reported 78.6% reported by Olatona et al., (2020) for normal weight. This may be as a result of the higher civilization of the adolescents in Lagos compared to the study are thus a better nutritional education. Al-lahham et al., (2019) reported 4% underweight, 69.9% normal weight, 23.7% overweight while for obese, 2.4% was reported in a research study on adolescent carried out in Palestinian on adolescents. Raru et al., (2022) in a study on adolescent girls in East Africa reported 16.5% and 2,4% for underweight and obese respectively. The Findings to research question two show that secondary school students in Ondo East Local Government Area consume recommended food items inadequately and

consume less recommended food items adequately. Specifically, the students inadequately consume roots and tubers, cereals and cereal product, fruits, fish and sea foods, legumes, nuts and seeds, and milk and milk products, but consume meat and eggs adequately. On the other hand, they consume oils and fats and soft drinks adequately, but consume condiments excessively. Vartanian et al., (2007) noted that an excessive consumption of soft drinks, sweets and fast food combined with a low intake of fruit, vegetables and dairy products is common during adolescence (secondary school age bracket). As touching their dietary pattern, the present study found out that students eat three meals in a day, sometimes skip lunch, got their food majorly through purchase, eat sweets in-between means and consume snacks.

Findings to research question three show that among secondary school students in Ondo East Local Government Area, inadequate dietary patterns can negatively impact the overall health of adolescents by causing diseases, lead to decreased academic performance, contribute to unhealthy eating habits among adolescents, hinder their ability to make informed dietary choices, and result in unhealthy adulthood. This is in line with the assertion of MU (2017) that eating pattern is of major concern because it can lead to overweight and a higher probability of chronic Non Communicable Diseases (NCDs), such as obesity, diabetes, high blood pressure, dyslipidemia, cardiovascular diseases and cancer later in life.

Findings to research question four show that the dietary pattern of secondary school students in Ondo East Local Government Area is affected by economic status, financial constraints of the parents, cultural background, exorbitant cost of nutritious food, personal preference for sweetened meals, and parental preference. Previous studies have shown that the nutritional status adolescence associated with various factors such as the intake of energy and nutrients, gender, education, habits of consumption of fiber (fruits and vegetables), physical activity, smoking, and genetic factors is nutritional status of parents of teenagers (Soliman, 2022).

The test of the first null hypothesis reveals that there is no significant relationship between the dietary pattern and nutritional status of secondary school students in Ondo East Local Government Area. This finding is not in agreement with the finding of Malik and Hu, (2022) that the consumption of sweetened drinks can be associated with the nutritional status of schoolchildren. This may be because there are several other factors that contribute to the nutritional status of children other than dietary pattern which are not captured in the present study. One of such factor is the physical activity level of the children.

The test of the second null hypothesis reveals that there is no significant difference in the effects of inappropriate dietary pattern between male and female students of public Secondary Schools of in Ondo East Local Government Area of Ondo State. Literature shows that gender has not been identified as a risk factor for malnutrition, although in the study of Wamani et al., (2007), 6.4% of boys were stunted compared to 5.7% of girls.

The test of the third null hypothesis reveals that there is no significant difference in factors affecting dietary pattern between male and female students of public Secondary Schools of in Ondo East Local Government Area of Ondo State. In a previous study of the factors associated with being overweight, Manyanga, et al. (2014) found that girls had a higher prevalence of overweight among school-going adolescents in five African countries, including Benin, than boys. The same observation was made by Muthuri et al., (2016) among children and youths within school-age in sub-Saharan Africa. On the other hand, a higher prevalence of overweight among boys 3.7% and 1.4% among girls has been reported among children attending public schools in the city of Rabat, Morocco, though this difference can be attributed to the heterogeneity of the criteria used to classify overweight and obesity.

v. Conclusion and Recommendation

The study examined the dietary pattern and nutritional status of adolescents in public secondary schools in Ondo East local Government Area of Ondo State. The findings of the study showed that there are some factors influencing dietary pattern and nutritional status of adolescents in public secondary schools and that though the average nutritional status of the secondary school students in the study area is normal, their dietary pattern is still however worrisome. The study further identified effects of inappropriate dietary pattern on secondary school students in the study area, so also does it examine challenges in determining the dietary pattern of adolescents in public secondary in Ondo East Local Government Area. Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. School administrators and counselors should give orientation to secondary school students about the detriments of a poor dietary pattern.
2. Stakeholders in the educational systems such as the government and non-governmental organizations should collaborate to provide a school feeding for adolescents in secondary schools just as it is practiced with children in primary schools.
3. Parents should pay close attention to the dietary patterns of their children at home and should indulge more in the provision of home-made meals to their children.

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